

MEAN VALUE OF THE ADDITIVE ANALOGUE OF SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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Abstract For any positive integer n , let $Sdf(n)$ denotes the Smarandance double factorial function, then $Sdf(n)$ is defined as least positive integer m such that $m!!$ is divisible by n . In this paper, we study the mean value properties of the additive analogue of $Sdf(n)$ and give an interesting mean value formula for it.

Keywords: Smarandance function; Additive Analogue; Mean value formula

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , let $Sdf(n)$ denotes the Smarandance double factorial function, then $Sdf(n)$ defined the least positive integer n such that $m!!$ is divisible by n , where

$$m!! = \begin{cases} 2 \cdot 4 \cdots m, & \text{if } 2|m; \\ 1 \cdot 3 \cdots m, & \text{if } 2 \nmid m. \end{cases}$$

In reference [2], Professor Jozsef Sandor defined the following analogue of Smarandance double factorial function as:

$$Sdf_1(2x) = \min\{2m \in N : 2x \leq (2m)!!\}, x \in (1, \infty),$$

$$Sdf_1(2x + 1) = \min\{2m + 1 \in N : (2x + 1) \leq (2m + 1)!!\}, x \in (1, \infty),$$

which is defined on a subset of real numbers. Clearly $Sdf_1(n) = m$ if $x \in ((m - 2)!!, m!!]$ for $m \geq 2$, therefore this function is defined for $x \geq 1$.

About the arithmetical properties of $Sdf(n)$, many people had ever studied it. But for the mean value properties of $Sdf_1(n)$, it seems that no one have studied before. The main purpose of this paper is to study the mean value properties of $Sdf_1(n)$, and obtain an interesting mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following:

Theorem. For any real number $x \geq 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} Sdf_1(n) = \frac{2x \ln x}{\ln \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x(\ln x)(\ln \ln \ln x)}{(\ln \ln x)^2}\right).$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

In this section, we shall complete the proof of the theorem. First we need the following one simple Lemma. That is,

Lemma. *For any fixed positive integer m and n with $(m-2)!! < n \leq m!!$, we have the asymptotic formula*

$$m = \frac{2 \ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{(\ln n)(\ln \ln \ln n)}{(\ln \ln n)^2}\right).$$

Proof. To complete the proof the Lemma, we separate it into two cases:

(I) If $m = 2u$, we have $(2u-2)!! < n \leq (2u)!!$. Taking the logistic computation in the two sides of the inequality, we get

$$(u-1) \ln 2 + \sum_{i=1}^{u-1} \ln i < \ln n \leq u \ln 2 + \sum_{i=1}^u \ln i. \quad (1)$$

Then using the Euler's summation formula we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^u \ln i = \int_1^u \ln t dt + \int_1^u (t - [t])(\ln t)' dt = u \ln u - u + O(\ln u) \quad (2)$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^{u-1} \ln i = \sum_{i=1}^u \ln i + O(\ln u) = u \ln u - u + O(\ln u). \quad (3)$$

Combining (1), (2) and (3), we can easily deduce that

$$\ln n = u \ln u + (\ln 2 - 1)u + O(\ln u). \quad (4)$$

So

$$u = \frac{\ln n}{\ln u + (\ln 2 - 1)} + O(1). \quad (5)$$

Similarly, we continue taking the logistic computation in two sides of (5), then we also have

$$\ln u = \ln \ln n + O(\ln \ln u) \quad (6)$$

and

$$\ln \ln u = O(\ln \ln \ln n). \quad (7)$$

Hence, by (5), (6) and (7) we have

$$u = \frac{\ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{(\ln n)(\ln \ln \ln n)}{(\ln \ln n)^2}\right).$$

This completes the proof of the first case.

(II) If $m = 2u + 1$, we have $(2u - 1)!! < n \leq (2u + 1)!!$. Taking the logistic computation in the two sides of the inequality, we get

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2u} \ln i - (u \ln 2 + \sum_{i=1}^u \ln i) < \ln n \leq \sum_{i=1}^{2u+1} \ln i - (u \ln 2 + \sum_{i=1}^u \ln i). \quad (8)$$

Then using the Euler's summation formula we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2u} \ln i = \int_1^{2u} \ln t dt + \int_1^{2u} (t - [t])(\ln t)' dt = 2u \ln u + 2(\ln 2 - 1)u + O(\ln u) \quad (9)$$

and

$$\sum_{i=1}^{2u+1} \ln i = \sum_{i=1}^{2u} \ln i + O(\ln 2u + 1) = 2u \ln u + 2(\ln 2 - 1)u + O(\ln u). \quad (10)$$

From (2), (3), (8), (9) and (10) we have

$$\ln n = u \ln u + (\ln 2 - 1)u + O(\ln u).$$

Therefore, we may obtain (5).

Using the similar method on the above, we may have

$$u = \frac{\ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{(\ln n)(\ln \ln \ln n)}{(\ln \ln n)^2}\right).$$

This completes the proof of the second case.

Combining the above two cases, we can easily get

$$m = \frac{2 \ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{(\ln n)(\ln \ln \ln n)}{(\ln \ln n)^2}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Lemma.

Now we use the above Lemma to complete the proof of Theorem. For any real number $x \geq 2$, by the definition of $Sdf_1(n)$ and the above Lemma we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} Sdf_1(n) &= \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ (m-2)!! < n \leq m!!}} m \\ &= \sum_{n \leq x} \left(\frac{2 \ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{(\ln n)(\ln \ln \ln n)}{(\ln \ln n)^2}\right) \right) \\ &= 2 \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\ln n}{\ln \ln n} + O\left(\frac{x(\ln x)(\ln \ln \ln x)}{(\ln \ln x)^2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

By the Euler's summation formula, we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\ln n}{\ln \ln n} &= \int_2^x \frac{\ln t}{\ln \ln t} dt + \int_2^x (t - [t]) \left(\frac{\ln t}{\ln \ln t} \right)' dt + \frac{\ln x}{\ln \ln x} (x - [x]) \\ &= \frac{x \ln x}{\ln \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln \ln x}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, from (11) and (12) we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} Sdf_1(n) = \frac{2x \ln x}{\ln \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x(\ln x)(\ln \ln \ln x)}{(\ln \ln x)^2}\right).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem.

References

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